

Cyanogen Compounds of Pentavalent Rhenium

M. C. Chakravorti

In the pentavalent state, rhenium forms a number of fairly stable complex compounds containing dioxo groups in the cation or anion, e.g., $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{py})_4]\text{Cl}^{1,2}$, $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]^3$, etc. All these compounds develop violet or deep red colour with acids. From such solutions Lobodinskii and Ivanov-Emin¹ have isolated the compounds $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}_3$, and $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{py})_4]\text{Cl}_2$. Recently Murmann and Forester⁴ have determined the acid association constants of $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{en})_2]^+$ type compounds. It has been found interesting to study the action of acids on the cyanide complex, $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$.

On addition of HCl to an aqueous solution of $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$, the orange-yellow colour turns deep violet. The same colour is also observed when the aqueous solution is passed through a column of cation-exchange resin of the type Amberlite IR 120 (H). The addition of proton to the cyanide compound may be depicted in two ways:

The successive acid association constants have been determined by Bjerrum's method by potentiometric titration of a solution of $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$ with a standard acid solution, the ionic strength being maintained at 0.5 with KNO_3 . The acid association constants have been found to be $\log K_1=4.2$ and $\log K_2=1.4$ at 27° . The third association is extremely weak.

The acid solution slowly loses HCN. It is not therefore possible to isolate the free acid $\text{H}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$ or $\text{H}[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2(\text{CN})_4]$. On evaporation of an aqueous solution of $\text{K}_3[\text{ReO}_2(\text{CN})_4]$, containing excess of dilute HCl over solid KOH, crystals of KCl first separated, which were removed. The dried mass was extracted with ethanol. After evaporation, the residue was extracted with acetone. The solution was evaporated and dried in

1. *J. Gen. Chem. USSR*, 1943, 13, 253; *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1959, 4, 1762.
2. Chakravorti, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 81.
3. Klemm and Frischmuth, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1937, 230, 215.
4. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 1383.

vacuum over solid KOH. The deep pink, almost black, crystalline substance on analysis corresponds to the formula $\text{ReO}(\text{CN})_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. [Found: Re, 59.0; C, 11.6; N, 13.0. Calc. for $\text{ReO}(\text{CN})_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Re, 58.9; C, 11.4; N, 13.3%].

The substance is highly soluble in water, ethanol, and acetone, forming a deep brown solution. An aqueous solution reacts strongly acidic. The absorption spectra of the substance in water show a broad band in the region of 550 $\text{m}\mu$ and two sharp maxima in the regions of 210 and 270 $\text{m}\mu$.

The structure of the acid may be represented by a number of formulations: $\text{H}[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})_3]$, $\text{H}_2[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})_2(\text{CN})_3]$, $\text{H}_2[\text{ReO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})_3]$, $\text{H}_3[\text{ReO}_3(\text{OH})(\text{CN})_3]$, $\text{H}_4[\text{ReO}_4(\text{CN})_3]$. The pH of a $1.20 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution is 2.1, suggesting that the acid is strong.

Conductometric titration of the acid solution with alkali shows two breaks. In potentiometric titration, a sharp rise in pH is observed in the neighbourhood of the first equivalence point; on keeping, the pH , however, falls rapidly. The acid in solution thus appears to exist in equilibrium between a strong monobasic one, $\text{H}[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{CN})_3]$ and a dibasic one, $\text{H}_2[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})_2(\text{CN})_3]$, the former being slowly converted into the dibasic form during neutralisation. Further study on the structure of the acid and the isolation of its various salts is in progress.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF KALYANI,
KALYANI, W. BENGAL.

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